

KO'ZI OJIZ VA ZAYIF KO'RUVCHI O'QUVCHILARNING TA'LIM OLISHI.

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Annotasiya. Ko'rish qobiliyatini va eshitish qobiliyatini qisman yaxshilagan bolalar bor, ular maktabga, o'rta va hatto universitetlarga qo'shilish imkoniyatiga ega. Ammo, agar ular hech bo'lmaganda hech qanday hissiyotlari rivojlangan narsaga ega bo'lmasalar, ular o'zlari va atrofdagi dunyo o'rtasida vositachiga ega bo'lishlari kerak bo'lgan joyda ixtisoslashgan bo'lishadi.

Kalit so'z va iboralar: ko'rish, nogironlik, eshitish, ko'zi ojiz, ko'rish qobiliyati zayif.

EDUCATION OF BLIND AND WEAK-SIGHTED STUDENTS.

Abstract. There are children who have partially improved vision and hearing, they have the opportunity to join school, secondary and even universities. However, if they do not have at least something in which they have developed any emotions, they will be specialized where they need to have an intermediary between themselves and the world around them.

Key words: and phrases: vision, disability, hearing, blind, impaired vision.

ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ СЛЕПЫХ И СЛАБОВИДЯЩИХ УЧАЩИХСЯ.

Аннотация. Есть дети, у которых частично улучшилось зрение и слух, у которых есть возможность поступить в школу, среднюю школу и даже университеты. Однако, если у них нет хотя бы чего-то эмоционально развитого, они будут специализироваться на том, где им нужен посредник между собой и окружающим миром.

Ключевые слова: и фразы: зрение, инвалидность, слух, слепота, нарушение зрения.

So'nggi yillarda mamlakatimizda "Inson qadri uchun" tamoyili asosida nogironligi bo'lgan shaxslarni qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimini yanada takomillashtirish, xususan ko'zi ojiz va ko'rishda nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalarning jamiyatdagi o'rnini mustahkamlash yuzasidan zarur chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirildi. Mazkur yo'nalishdagi islohotlarning izchilligi va tizimligini ta'minlash, ko'zi ojiz va zaif ko'ruvchi bolalarning ta'lim olishi uchun yaratilgan shart-sharoitlarni yanada yaxshilash, ularning jamiyatga moslashuviga ko'maklashish hamda qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha ishlarni yangi bosqichga olib chiqish maqsadida, qator chora tadbirlar ko'rib borilmoqda.

Ko'zi ojiz bolalarga kiradi ko'rish va eshitish ma'nosida katta cheklovni nazarda tutadigan bir nechta nogironlik. Bu bolalar juda moslashtirilgan maxsus ta'lim va qo'llab-quvvatlash uslubiga muhtoj ular o'zlarining kundalik hayotlariga duch kelishlari uchun. Ko'pgina hollarda, ular karlar ekanligi aniqlangan bo'lsa-da, bu ularning ikkala hissiyotlari umuman buzilganligini anglatmaydi, balki qisman kamayishi mumkin.

Ko'zi ojiz bolalarning ta'limi har bir kishi ko'rsatadigan nogironlik turiga moslashtirilishi kerak. Ko'rish qobiliyatini va eshitish qobiliyatini qisman yaxshilagan bolalar bor, ular maktabga, o'rta va hatto universitetlarga qo'shilish imkoniyatiga ega. Ammo, agar ular hech bo'lmaganda hech qanday hissiyotlari rivojlangan narsaga ega bo'lmasalar, ular o'zlari va atrofdagi dunyo o'rtasida vositachiga ega bo'lishlari kerak bo'lgan joyda ixtisoslashgan bo'lishadi.

"Ko'rishida muammolari bo'lgan bolalar uchun ta'limning dastlabki o'zlashtirish davri asosan boshlang'ich sinflarga to'g'ri keladi. Ushbu bosqichda o'quvchilarga o'zaro va o'qituvchi bilan dastlabki muloqot o'rnatish, so'z boyligini oshirish, savodini chiqarish, mayda qo'l

motorikasini rivojlantirish hamda o‘z-o‘ziga xizmat qilish, predmet tasavvurini shakllantirish va ko‘ruv idrokini rivojlantirish, shuningdek, dastlabki matematik tasavvurlarni shakllantirish o‘rgatiladi. Bu esa, o‘quvchiga mazkur bosqichda boshlang‘ich ta‘limni mustahkam egallab olishiga yordam beradi.

Bundan tashqari, ko‘zi ojiz va zaif ko‘ruvchi bolalar davlat ixtisoslashtirilgan ta‘lim muassasalarida tayyorlov guruhlarining ochilishi hamda moslashtirilgan o‘quv dasturlarining yaratilishi ko‘zi ojiz va zaif ko‘ruvchi o‘quvchilarning umumta‘lim maktablarida joriy etilgan inklyuziv hamda boshlang‘ich tayanch korreksion sinflarga kengroq jalb etilishini va ularning inklyuziv ta‘lim olish huquqini ta‘minlashga xizmat qiladi”, - deyiladi vazirlik ma‘lumotida. Ko‘zi ojiz bolalar uchun ixtisoslashtirilgan maktab-internatlarda bolalar va o‘qituvchilar uchun zarur shart-sharoitlarni yaratish majburiy tartibda amalga oshiriladigan ishlar sirasiga kiradi. Ko‘zi ojiz o‘qituvchilar faoliyatini samarali olib borishi uchun maktab-internat kotib tayinlaydi. Umuman olganda, bu maktablardagi muhit ko‘zi ojiz pedagoglar uchun eng ijobiy muhitdir, chunki ular bu yerda ko‘rish qobiliyati cheklangan kishilarning mehnat qobiliyati haqidagi salbiy stereotiplarga va xurofotlarga to‘la jamiyatdan himoyalangan o‘z muhitlarida ishlashadi.

Ta‘kidlash joizki, ko‘plab pedagogik oliy o‘quv yurtlarini tamomlagan ko‘zi ojiz talabalar aynan bir vaqtlar o‘zlari tahsil olgan maxsus maktablarida ish topishga intilishadi, chunki u yerda ular uchun barcha zarur sharoitlar yaratilgan. Bundan tashqari, maxsus maktab-internat o‘qituvchilari oddiy umumta‘lim maktablari o‘qituvchilariga nisbatan ancha ahamiyatli ijtimoiy himoya bilan ta‘minlangan.

Lekin maxsus maktablar hammani ham sig‘diraolmaydi! Butun respublika bo‘ylab ko‘zi ojiz va zaif ko‘ruvchi bolalar uchun faqat 14 ta maktab-internat faoliyat ko‘rsatmoqda, ularda 2830 dan ortiq bola o‘qiydi va 823 o‘qituvchi va 606 tarbiyachi ishlaydi. Ko‘zi ojizlar jamiyati ma‘lumotlariga ko‘ra, O‘zbekistonda 66 mingdan ortiq ko‘rish qobiliyati cheklangan shaxslar ro‘yxatga olinganini inobatga oladigan bo‘lsak, oliy ta‘lim muassasalarining barcha ko‘zi ojiz bitiruvchilarini ixtisoslashtirilgan maktablarda ishga joylashtirishning imkoni yo‘q.

Hozirgi vaqtda nogironligi bo‘lgan bolalarning 26,8 foizi ixtisoslashtirilgan maktablar va maktab-internatlarga qamrab olingan. O‘tgan yili qabul qilingan inklyuziv ta‘limni rivojlantirish konsepsiyasida 2025 yilgacha maktab-internatdagi bolalar sonini bosqichma-bosqich 16%ga qisqartirish va umumiy o‘rta ta‘lim muassasalarida o‘qiyotgan nogironligi bo‘lgan bolalarning ulushini hozirgi 16,5% dan 40% gacha oshirish ko‘zda tutilgan.

Agar ko‘zi ojiz bola oddiy maktabga o‘qishga kirsa, u uchun barcha oqilona qulayliklar oldindan tayyorlanishi kerak — qulay formatlardagi (Brayl alifbosida, katta shriftda yoki audio formatida) o‘quv materiallari. Maktabda ko‘rish qobiliyati cheklangan o‘quvchiga individual yordam ko‘rsatadigan malakali o‘qituvchilarning mavjudligi ham muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Ko‘zi ojiz o‘qituvchilar O‘zbekistonda inklyuziv ta‘limni rivojlantirish uchun muhim inson resursiga aylanishi mumkin, chunki ular nafaqat ixtisoslashtirilgan pedagogik mahoratga ega (Brayl alifbosida yoki boshqa formatlarda bajarilgan uy vazifalari va nazorat ishlarini tekshirish), balki ko‘zi ojiz va zaif ko‘ruvchi o‘quvchilar bilan bo‘lishadigan hayotiy tajribaga ega. Bundan tashqari, agar ko‘zi ojiz o‘qituvchilar uchun zarur shart-sharoitlar yaratilsa, u holda ular nogironligi bo‘lmagan bolalarga ham ta‘lim berishlari mumkin.

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